

The Role of Religious Counselors in Dealing with Juvenile Delinquency

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Article History

Received: 10.11.2023

Accepted: 26.12.2023

Published: 05.01.2024

Abstract: Juvenile delinquency is becoming increasingly common nowadays, juvenile delinquency is now rampant in various areas in Indonesia. This is the focus of the researcher's attention in writing this article with the aim of educating teenagers who are irresponsible in their actions. Juvenile delinquency is a normal thing that occurs due to changes in physical, psychological and social aspects so that teenagers tend to ignore or reject existing regulations. Christian religious counselors become figures in assisting teenagers regarding teenagers' actions that harm others and can also harm themselves. Religious Counselors are Civil Servants who are given duties, responsibilities and full authority by authorized officials to carry out religious guidance and development counseling activities using religious languages. This research was carried out because researchers wanted to find out whether religious counselors could tackle juvenile delinquency which has been rampant to date. It is also hoped that religious counselors can become companions for juvenile delinquents who have fallen into cases of juvenile delinquency.

Keywords: Conversion Of Religion, Juvenile Delinquency.

Introduction

The extension is an up-led guard that can heal society "ill" through coaching in their respective groups. The extension is the person who interacts directly with the community. They become agent of change for the formation of religious and qualified communities. Communication ethics is also important in this case, because in conveying the truth or extension, an extension should still pay attention to communicating ethics. What the extension should be supposed to be insep or soothing, not even making the situation become more heat or complicated.¹

Adolescence is a transition phase from childhood to adulthood. A teenager can no longer be categorized as a child, but is also not mature enough to be called an adult. Teenagers are looking for the lifestyle that best suits them, often by trial and error even through many mistakes. The mistakes they make often make parents and their environment feel anxious and uncomfortable. However, this mistake was actually fun for his peers. This is because they are also still in the process of finding their identity. Mistakes that cause environmental irritation are what are often referred to as juvenile delinquency. Whether we want to admit it or not, adolescence is the most exciting period and at the same time brings the most problems, both for teenagers themselves and for their environment in general.² Adolescence is often known as a time of rebellion. During this period, teenagers who have just experienced puberty often show various emotional turmoil,

and face many problems, both at home, school and among friends. Today's juvenile delinquency, as has been widely reported by various media, is said to have exceeded normal limits. Many teenagers and minors are involved in delinquency which is very disturbing to society.³

Nowadays everything wants to be tried. Everything wants to be felt. Even though it is quite complicated and there are many problems that occur during this period, most teenagers can develop into normal teenagers.⁴ This normalcy can take the form of a relatively mild identity crisis; relationships with family, play groups, understanding of what is seen in the mass media and the education system are quite good. These teenagers have self-confidence, self-esteem, and have the ability to overcome personal problems. On the other hand, there are teenagers who do not have harmonious relationships within the family, play groups, the influence of mass media, and the educational process is not running normally. Various problems, for example, in terms of violations of morals or applicable regulations as well as crimes. If this individual is difficult to control, then that individual can be called a naughty teenager.

Juvenile delinquency is a normal thing that occurs due to changes in physical, psychological and social aspects so that teenagers tend to ignore or reject existing regulations. In the adolescent phase, a person needs the role of parents to prevent delinquency so that it remains within tolerable limits. Because if it

¹ Agustina Melina Sipahutar et al., "Cristian Religious Instructor Communication Ethics," *ELETTTRA: Jurnal pendidikan Penyuluhan Agama Kristen Institut Agama Kristen Negeri Tarutung* 1, no. 1 (2023): 21.

² Dadan Sumara Sumara, Sahadi Humaedi, and Meilanny Budiarti Santoso, "Juvenile Delinquency And Its Management," *Jurnal Penelitian & PPM* 4, no. 2 (2017): 436-53, <https://doi.org/10.24198/jppm.v4i2.14393>.

³ Lilis Karlina, "The Phenomenon Of Juvenile Delinquency," *Jurnal: Edukasi Nonformal* 1, no. 1 (2020): 147-58.

⁴ Esra Sitompul, "Pengaruh Bimbingan Guru Pendidikan Agama Krite Terhadap Pembentukan Perilaku Siswa," *Bhinneka: Jurnal Bintang Pendidikan Dan Bahasa* 1, no. 4 (2023): 45-58, <https://doi.org/10.59024/bhinneka.v1i4.361>.

is not handled properly, juvenile delinquency can turn into a criminal act that sends the perpetrator to prison.⁵

Research Methodology

The research method used is a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. The data collection method was carried out through literature study from various references sourced from research journals and books. Qualitative research is an approach to conducting research that focuses on natural phenomena or symptoms. Qualitative research is basic and naturalistic or natural, and cannot be carried out in the laboratory, but in the field. Therefore, this type of research is often called naturalistic inquiry or field study.⁶ Qualitative researchers begin their work by trying to understand the phenomena that concern them, with a very open mind, so as to form an interpretation. Next, the researcher compares one source with another source so that the researcher can feel confident that the information he has obtained is correct.⁷

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Religious Counselor

Religious Counselors are Civil Servants who are given duties, responsibilities and full authority by authorized officials to carry out religious guidance and development counseling activities using religious languages.⁸ A religious instructor is a person who is entrusted with providing enlightenment guidance regarding faith and guidance on the path of truth for those who are still far from spiritual reach. Religious instructors have a role and function in society to help direct, guide and explain like a lighthouse in society.

The role of counselors is oriented towards religious formation, understanding the reality of religious pluralism, and building religious moderation in order to achieve harmony between religious communities. In the Regulation of the Minister of Religion Number 516 of 2003 concerning Technical Instructions for Functional Positions of Religious Instructors and Credit Scores, it is stated that the task of instructors is to implement and develop programs of guidance or counseling and religious development activities through religious language.⁹

Juvenile Delinquency

Adolescence is the period when people are in their teens. A teenager can no longer be categorized as a child, but is also not mature enough to be called an adult. This is because teenagers are looking for the lifestyle that is most suitable for themselves, and this is often done using the trial and error method even though there are many mistakes. Every teenager has a different environment and background, such as economics, relationships, family, education, and so on. Wrong relationships are one of the

causes of juvenile delinquency.¹⁰ Especially in this day and age, for reasons of modernization, teenagers want to try things that should not be appropriate.¹¹ Adolescence does not seem to have a clear place, it is neither a child nor an adult. This is because teenagers are not yet able to fully master their physical and psychological functions. That's why we often hear about adolescence as a transitional period.¹² Every teenager has a different background such as environment, economy, relationships, family, education, and others. Wrong relationships are one of the causes of juvenile delinquency. Especially in this day and age, for reasons of modernization, many teenagers want to try things that should not be appropriate. Juvenile delinquency is a natural thing that occurs due to changes in physical, psychological and social aspects that make teenagers tend to ignore or oppose applicable regulations. During adolescence, the role of parents is needed to prevent delinquency so that it remains within the limits of tolerance. Because if it is not handled properly, juvenile delinquency can turn into a crime that sends the perpetrator to prison. Parents are the first environment that can prevent this by implementing appropriate parenting patterns. Unfortunately, not all parents are able to respond to this well.

Factors of Juvenile Delinquency

a) Factors Within Adolescents: Self-control acts as a psychological mediator of various behaviors. The ability to distance oneself from urge behavior and satisfy non-adaptive desires. Individuals who have high self-control are able to direct their behavior, whereas individuals with low self-control will have the impact of being unable to comply with rules of behavior and actions so that the individual can no longer resist temptation and impulses.¹³ b) Household Environmental Factors: Several external factors that often become the background for juvenile delinquency include lack of love from parents/family, broken home (either due to divorce or frequent parental quarrels), negative influence from peers or playmates, a bad environment, and progress. information and technology that is detrimental.¹⁴ Households are one of the factors in which juvenile delinquency occurs, where the background of family life is less harmonious, children will have uncontrolled lives. As a result, juvenile delinquency will become more common without control from parents as mentors in the family, especially in guiding children on the right path, lack of family attention will also result in things that the child does not want to do. c) Community Environmental Factors; Indeed, adolescence is a time when a child begins to search for their identity. If they are in the wrong company, it could have a bad impact on themselves and others, such as juvenile delinquency which has been rampant recently. Apart from family, the environment around the house also influences a child's development. Even though you have a conducive family, a poor home environment can also have a negative impact on children. Because more or less, children don't

⁵ Utami Adristinindya Cirtra Nur and Raharjo Santoso Tri, "Parental Upbringing and Juvenile Delinquency," *Focus : Jurnal Pekerjaan Sosial* 4, no. 1 (2021): 12.

⁶ Abdussamad Zuchi, *Qualitative Research Methods* (Makasar: Syakir Media Press iii, 2021), 30.

⁷ Syafrida Hafni Sahir, *Research Methodology* (Bojonegoro-Jawa Timur: Publisher KBM Indonesia, 2022), 8.

⁸ Munawiroh, "The Role of Education in Religious Counseling in Society," *EDUKASI: Research Journal of Religion and Religious Education* 12, no. 2 (2014): 226.

⁹ Peranginangin Enda Dwi Karina et al., "Challenges and Strategies of Christian Religious Instructors in Implementing the North Tapanuli Regency Program," *Christian Humanities Journal* 6, no. 1 (2022): 23–43.

¹⁰ Purniasih, "Reconstructing the Role of Parents in Shaping the Personality of the Child," *Exousia: Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Kristen* 1, no. 1 (2022): 1–9.

¹¹ Karlina, "The Phenomenon Of Juvenile Delinquency. journal: Nonformal Education. 1 no.1 (2020).149."

¹² Fakhru Rijal, "Development of the Religious Spirit in Adolescence (Al-Murahiqah)," *PIONIR: Journal of Education* 5, no. 2 (2016): 59–70.

¹³ Ramadona Dwi Marsela and Mamat Supriatna, "Self-Control: Definition and Factors," *Journal of Innovative Counseling: Theory, Practice & Research* 3, no. 2 (2019): 67.

¹⁴ Budi Artini et al., "Analysis of Factors Influencing Juvenile Delinquency," *Journal of Nursing* 7, no. 1 (2018): 44–50.

only socialize in their home environment but also with friends around their house.¹⁵ d) School Environmental Factors: The school environment is one of the factors that causes juvenile delinquency. It is evident in our lives today that juvenile delinquency originates from school. Where school is a meeting place for students who come from different family backgrounds, because of this, teenagers' curiosity about things will become even higher. For example, skipping school, drinking alcoholic beverages, promiscuous sex and so on are forms of juvenile delinquency that we often see and hear about today. e) Social Media Factors: Social media has a huge influence on the social pressure felt by teenagers. Teenagers often feel burdened to meet the expectations of their friends on social media in terms of physical appearance, lifestyle and relationships. This can give rise to feelings of insecurity and social anxiety in teenagers, which ultimately affects their behavior. This feeling of depression arises because teenagers compare their friends' posts on social media with the real life they live.¹⁶

Religious Counselors in Overcoming Juvenile Delinquency

a). Provide guidance and counseling : Guidance and Counseling is a support service for students, both individually and in groups, so that they can be independent and develop optimally in developing their personal life, social life, learning abilities and career planning. This service is provided through various types of supporting services and activities, based on applicable norms.¹⁷ The following is guidance that can be provided by religious counselors, namely: 1) Personal guidance: services to develop abilities and overcome personal and personality problems related to intellectual, affective and physical-motor aspects. 2) Social guidance: services to develop abilities and overcome social problems in family, school and community life; in terms of working together and interacting with peers, adults or younger students. 3) Tutoring: services to optimize development and overcome problems in the learning process with teachers and independent learning at home and at school. 4) Career guidance: services to plan and prepare for career development. b) Invite teenagers to get involved in positive activities: Religious instructors are able to invite teenagers to be involved in positive activities, namely teenagers are involved in spiritual activities and teenagers are able to serve according to the faith they follow. c) Increasing parental involvement in teenagers' lives: Parents are involved in the counseling plan so that the counseling carried out can achieve the stated goals. d) Use educational sanctions

CONCLUSION

Adolescence is a transition period from childhood to adulthood. A teenager can no longer be called a child, but he is still not mature enough to be called an adult. He is looking for a lifestyle that is most suitable for him and this is often done through trial and error, even though there are many mistakes. So, juvenile delinquency is adolescent behavior that deviates from the norms or rules that exist in society. Juvenile delinquency is a form of symptom experienced by children which is caused by factors, both family, friends and society. This makes us increasingly challenged to deal with all forms of juvenile delinquency that exist in the

wider community, and has disturbed the public regarding behavior and actions that do not pay attention to human values.

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¹⁶ Daffa Aqiilah, Denny Soestrisna As, and Agung Fauzi, "The Impact of Social Media on Juvenile Delinquency," *Edusociata Journal of Sociological Education* 6, no. (2023). 221.

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